

Synthesis, sintering and microstructure of beta-tricalcium phosphate for prosthetic applications

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A method is described for preparing dense, polycrystalline beta-tricalcium phosphate. The phase composition of the precipitate made by mixing $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ and H_3PO_4 solutions with subsequent drying and calcining has been studied as a function of initial mixing Ca/P molar ratio. Pure beta-tricalcium phosphate is prepared with initial Ca/P = 1.2 and without any pH control. Effects of milling time of calcined powder on the sintering behavior and microstructural development examined. Grinding for a longer time helps in achieving a relatively high density and fine-grain microstructure at 1200° . The synthesized powder of beta-TCP shows good biocompatibility and no cytotoxicity.

Calcium phosphate bioceramics have gained a distinct place in the biomaterials research field. The two forms of calcium phosphate ceramics that have received the most attention are hydroxyapatite (HA) and beta-tricalcium phosphate (beta-TCP). Hydroxyapatite as implant materials are bioactive while those of beta-tricalcium phosphate are bioresorbable. The purpose of a resorbable biomaterial is to provide a temporary scaffold or space filler until such time as a body can replace it. Beta-tricalcium phosphate has been used in several forms in animals and humans to repair many types of defects in bone. Beta-tricalcium phosphate blocks have been implanted in rats¹ and in dogs² successfully. Beta-TCP powder or granules have been used to repair open apices, periapical and marginal periodontal defects and alveolar bony defects in humans^{3,4}. However, when used as a biomaterial for alveolar ridge augmentation, the rate of biodegradation of beta-TCP has been shown to be too fast. To slow the rate of biodegradation, composite ceramics consisting of beta-TCP and HA have also been studied⁵. Beta-TCP by itself has not been reported to cause any adverse reactions in animal or human tissues³.

There are many procedures for production of beta-TCP but for practical use, precipitation is more important. Jarcho *et al.*⁶ described a method for the production of beta-TCP from $\text{Ca}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ and $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{HPO}_4$ solutions by doping with catalytic amount of ammonium sulphate. Using same reagents, Bako and Kotsis⁷ prepared beta-TCP without ammonium sulfate as a catalyst; pH was controlled at 9.1. It was also observed by them that without pH control the product was beta- $\text{Ca}_2\text{P}_2\text{O}_7$. Akao *et al.*⁸ prepared beta-TCP from $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ and H_3PO_4 without using ammonium sulfate as a catalyst; pH of the solution was maintained above 6.0 during the course of reaction by adding 3% ammonia.

In the present study, an attempt has been made to

prepare beta-TCP in a relatively simple manner from $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ and H_3PO_4 without controlling the pH of the reaction and without using sulfate as a catalyst. The powder so prepared was characterised for purity and phase content. Finally, the powder in the compact form was fired at different temperatures and time to study its densification behaviour and microstructure.

Results and Discussion

The X-ray diffraction patterns of powders with a initial mixing Ca/P molar ratio of 1.5 to 1.2 and calcined at 1000° are given in Fig. 1. The XRD pattern (Fig. 1a) of powder with initial Ca/P ratio of 1.5 contained peaks corresponding to hydroxyapatite only and no other peak was detected. This result was in agreement with the observation made by Jarcho *et al.*⁶ who reported that reacting calcium and phosphate in the correct tricalcium phosphate stoichiometric ratio (Ca/P = 1.5) frequently resulted in the production of powder with Ca/P >1.50. The XRD pattern (Fig. 1b) of powder with a initial Ca/P ratio of 1.4 showed the presence of both hydroxyapatite and beta-TCP. The powders with initial Ca/P ratio of 1.3 and 1.2 indicated the presence of only beta-TCP phase in their XRD patterns (Figs. 1c and 1d respectively). Thus, the observation made by the earlier researchers⁹ that the formation of different phases of calcium phosphate in solution depends on the solution conditions, namely, pH, temperature, ionic concentration, Ca/P molar ratio and presence of inorganic or organic elements, has been corroborated by our findings also.

The two powders which on calcining at 1000° produced beta-TCP were further calcined at 1200° , the optimum temperature of sintering, and their XRD patterns revealed that only powder with initial Ca/P ratio of 1.2 remained

Fig. 1. X-Ray diffraction patterns for the synthesized powders with different initial mixing Ca/P molar ratio and calcined at 1000° : (a) Ca/P = 1.5, (b) Ca/P = 1.4, (c) Ca/P = 1.3, (d) Ca/P = 1.2.

stable at that temperature (Fig. 2a). The other one (initial Ca/P = 1.3) indicated the presence of α -TCP along with β -TCP (Fig. 2b). Hence, pure β -TCP ceramics can be

prepared by using initial mixing Ca/P ratio of 1.2 without any pH control and sulfate catalyst. Analytical data (CaO, 54.25; P₂O₅, 45.11 wt.%) of the powder revealed that the powder was stoichiometric in nature and had high purity.

Fig. 2. X-Ray diffraction patterns for the synthesized powders with different initial mixing Ca/P molar ratio, calcined at 1000° and subsequently at 1200° : (a) Ca/P = 1.2, (b) Ca/P = 1.3.

So for further studies in this experiment only this powder was used.

The powder after calcining at 1000° was ground for 5 and 20 h and designated as T-5 and T-20, respectively. The particle size analysis shows that in case of T-5, only 3.8% particles lie below 1.5 micron whereas in case of T-20, 16.0% particles exist below 1.5 micron, and even below 0.1 micron, 6.9% particles remain. The median diameters of T-5 and T-20 are 4.56 and 3.27 micron, respectively. The compacts made out of T-5 were fired at different temperatures with a holding time of 1 h. The variation in bulk density with temperature showed that as the sintering temperature increased from 1000° to 1250°, the bulk density increased from 1.88 to 2.78 g/ml. The increase upto 1100° was small and after 1200° there was a significant increase in density but even then the body did not densify and a relative density of only 92% was achieved at 1250°. The plots of the sintered bulk density against sintering time data at 1200° revealed that bulk density in case of T-5 increased quickly in the early stage of sintering and there was a large increase from 2 to 3 h. After 3 h the increase in bulk density slowed down and there was a marginal increase in density upto 5 h. At 3 h the bulk density was 2.70 g/ml which increased to 2.78 g/ml at 5 h which corresponded to a relative density of only 90.6%. In case of T-20, it was observed that the bulk density increased drastically from 2.42 g/ml for 0 h to 2.90 g/ml for 1 h, and thereafter there was

no appreciable change in density. The maximum density achieved for 5 h was 2.95 g/ml which corresponded to 97.36% relative density (theor. density = 3.03 g/ml).

The possible explanation for the difference in sintering behaviour between T-5 and T-20 lies in the presence of agglomerates in them. It may be mentioned here that both the powders were prepared by precipitation method and calcined at 1000° and the only difference between them is in milling time. Heat treatment during calcination is believed to have changed the loose agglomerates formed during powder preparation into hard agglomerates or aggregates. During the milling process mechanical force breaks down the aggregates. The milling time for T-5 and T-20 was 5 and 20 h, respectively. Because of the difference in milling time, T-5 is expected to contain more agglomerates of larger size than T-20 and this was confirmed by the particle (agglomerate) size analysis. When T-5 and T-20 compacts were fired at 1200° for 5 h, the relative density achieved was 90.6 and 97.4%, respectively. Since T-5 samples contained large agglomerates, they might not have collapsed completely during sintering, resulting in the formation of large voids. If the voids are larger than the surrounding grains they may never be removed during the sintering process and would cause densification to halt at some finite level below the theoretical density. This exactly was the case with T-5. The longer milling time in case of T-20 reduced the agglomerate size to a great extent and thus did not affect the sinterability adversely.

Optical micrographs of T-5 and T-20 samples, sintered at 1200°/5 h and thermally etched at 1100°/0.5 h showed that the microstructures are not similar. There was evidence of pores larger than the surrounding grains in T-5 sample. These pores were nearly spherical and non-uniformly distributed in the structure. The grains were irregular and of varying sizes. As compared with T-5, grains and pores were smaller in T-20 sample. The pores in this case were smaller than most of the individual grain and randomly distributed. These microstructures also provided evidence to our above explanation for differing sintering behaviour of the two samples under identical sintering condition.

Sintered beta-TCP did not exhibit toxic effects and showed good biocompatibility.

Conclusions : Pure beta-TCP powder can be prepared by using initial mixing Ca/P ratio of 1.2 without any pH control and sulfate catalyst. Grinding of calcined powder for a longer time helped in obtaining a dense body at 1200°/5 h. Sintered material has promise for bone implant applications.

Experimental

Calcium hydroxide (A.R.; 0.7–0.6 mol) was dispersed in preboiled distilled water (1 dm³). The suspension was vigorously stirred at 80°. A solution of orthophosphoric acid (A.R.; 0.5–0.4 mol) in distilled water (1 dm³) was

added dropwise at the rate of 10 ml/min. The pH of the suspension was 8–9. The resulting milky gelatinous precipitate was allowed to age for 20 h, then filtered and washed with distilled water. The filter-cake was dried at 70° and calcined at 1000° for 3 h. A few powders were calcined at 1200° to check the thermal stability of the same. The calcined product was ground in a planetary mill in isopropanol medium.

Phases of the calcined products were identified by X-ray powder diffraction using nickel-filtered CuK-alpha radiation in the two-theta range 10–60 degree. The diffraction patterns were compared with the data base in the American Society for Testing and Materials powder diffraction files. The Ca/P atomic ratio in beta-TCP was measured by chemical analysis. Standard EDTA titration technique was used for the analysis of calcium. The phosphate content was determined spectrophotometrically as phosphomolybdate. The particle size distribution of powder was determined by Sedigraph.

The beta-TCP powder was compacted at room temperature in a steel die under a uniaxial stress of 120 MPa. The green compacts were fired in air at 1000–1250° with varying soaking time. Sintered density was determined by following Archimedes' principle.

Sintered specimen of beta-TCP was ground and the powder was used for toxicity and biocompatibility test¹⁰.

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